

Is Chatgpt changing our learning?

After reading articles about ChatGPT, a word which stands for Chat Generative Pre trained transformer, in different journals and hearing this topic in conversations among my colleagues, it aroused my curiosity to see how effective this chat bot could be in producing text and answering questions.

In the past I have used a chatbot from my bank's website when I wanted to know an answer with regards to my account and no human voice was available to answer, or if I had a question about a flight ticket claim and the phone lines were too busy. In both cases the answers I have got were disastrous, as the machine only picked up key words and couldn't help me solve my problem.

Thus, here I was in front of my computer, and asked ChatGPT to give me a description on the use of the Mini Sphero, a small robot that I often use in my classes. The outcome was surprising as it gave me a full description of this robot and how it can be used. A time saver if I had to write the description myself to my pupils.

Thus, the question is how this AI (Artificial intelligence) tool going to change our lives and the way we learn, think, and do things.

Although, I am sceptical of the potential dangers that this learning machine can bring us, some people seemed very enthusiastic about this tool. I recently followed a podcast from Dr. Monica Burns, an educational technology expert in the USA, (2023) where she suggested using ChatGPT as a precious time saver tool for teachers.

Some examples mentioned in her podcast were that this tool could be used to create email reminders, help with research by giving primary resources on any specific subject, revise emails and even rewrite them for you to make the message friendlier, or concise or serious or whatever you would like it to be. It can also help a teacher with the phrasing of given personal feedback to pupils. In order words it can be your jumpstart if one is running out of time or ideas.

Moreover, this tool can write essays, create poems, answer reading comprehension questions, etc. The perfect assistant as it excels our human expectation.

On the other hand, beware that this tool can also generate distorting articles, impersonate people online, automate the production of abusive or fake content online including social media, automate the production of spam as explained by Alec Radford, et al. (2019). One should add what about plagiarism, since ChatGPT is a machine fed by eight million web pages and has 1.5 billion parameters (Radford, et. al 2019; García-Peñalvo 2023). What happens to creativity, literacy, and a writer's identity? Could a machine produce faster and perhaps more efficiently than my own writing? García-Peñalvo, 2023 describes it as the omission of authorship and calls for a need to revise the ethical considerations when using this tool.

Despite these risks Professor John Naughton, (2023) said ChatGPT is here to stay and thus one should see it more as an opportunity to change our human competences. His theory is that with time it will become a "mundane tool as Excel".

But until then, ChatGPT will change the way we produce and consume literacy. Even though there are tools like Turnitin and Viper to identify plagiarism on a text. This artificial intelligence produces writings that are more complex and taken from a wide range of sources making it complicated to detect it. (Sample, 2023; García-Peñalvo, 2023)

Moreover, many schools and universities have decided to ban the use of this chat bot (Caitlin, 2023; Maya 2023 and France 24, 2023). However, I do not believe this is the right measure to take as students will still be able to use outside the institution. It is for us educators to start changing our methods for teaching and assessing.

One should start with writing an ethical charter as to how this tool could be used in education, journalism, medicine, communication just to mention a few examples.

There is a need to teach critical thinking with regards to texts written by this machine. Naughton, 2023 recommends that teachers need to change their assessment. Instead of asking students to write an essay, one may ask to get ChatGPT to write it and after they should be able to do a critique

of what has been written by this machine and how will have they done it differently.

ChatGPT can be biased and discriminatory as it only reproduces the information that it has been fed. When one signs up to open an account with ChatGPT, a message appears with the warning that the language use by this tool could be offensive or biased. Thus, the importance to teach students to check for the biased language and the veracity of information.

Respect of authorship is another factor to take in consideration. Students should be taught to identify and check if a particular text has been written before by someone else.

Lastly, I think we should embrace the potential that this artificial intelligence can bring us. It could be a very good assistant not only for teachers, like Dr. Burns mentioned in her podcast but it can very well an assistant to students, especially those who are struggling with writing due to dyslexia, dysgraphia or those who have an attention deficit and can not think of any ideas to write about.

ChatGPT could be an assistant for creating reminders about homework activities or project deadlines. Children in the autism spectrum could benefit from this tool which can reassure them about answering multiple times the same question without losing patience. All these suggestions of course need to be accompanied by trained teachers or occupational therapists.

ChatGPT can provide a personalized path to students' learning which will allow to make adaptations whenever necessary. Nevertheless we should remain critical and constantly ask ourselves if we are learning or is it the machine taking the place of knowledge?

References:

Burns, M. (2023, January 30). 10 things teachers can do with ChatGPT to save time. <https://classtechtips.com/2023/01/30/chatgpt-to-save-time/>

<https://classtechtips.com/2023/01/30/chatgpt-to-save-time/>

Caitlin, C. (2023, January 22) Queensland public schools to join NSW in banning students from ChatGPT. *The Guardian*
https://www.theguardian.com/australia-news/2023/jan/23/queensland-public-schools-to-join-nsw-in-banning-students-from-chatgpt?CMP=Share_AndroidApp_Other

France 24 (2023, January 27). Top French university bans students from using ChatGPT. https://www.theguardian.com/us-news/2023/jan/06/new-york-city-schools-ban-ai-chatbot-chatgpt?CMP=Share_AndroidApp_Other

Garcia-Peñalvo, F.J. (2023, January 24) The perception of artificial intelligence in educational contexts after the launch of ChatGPT: Disruption or panic? *Education in the Knowledge Society* 24. Ediciones Universidad de Salamanca | <https://doi.org/10.14201/eks.31279>

Naughton, J. (2023, January 7). The ChatGPT bot is causing panic now, but it will soon be as mundane a tool as Excel. *The Guardian*
<https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2023/jan/07/chatgpt-bot-excel-ai-chatbot-tech>

Randorf, A. et.al (2019, February 15). Better Language Models and their implications. *Open AI*. <https://openai.com/blog/better-language-models/>

Sample, I. (2023, January 26) How will ChatGPT transform creative work? *The Guardian*. https://www.theguardian.com/science/audio/2023/jan/26/how-will-chatgpt-transform-creative-work-podcast?CMP=Share_AndroidApp_Other